

**THE IMPORTANCE OF USING BODY LANGUAGE IN OUR SPEECH
FOR TEACHING ENGLISH.**

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Abstract. In English teaching, with the constant reform of teaching methods, body language as a kind of nonverbal language plays a very significant role in the interaction between teachers and students. It not only can express the speakers' intention more accurately and effectively, simplify the teaching instruction, stimulate the students' interest, optimize the purpose of English teaching and enhance teaching effectiveness, but also can help improve the students' ability of listening, speaking, reading and so on. This article discusses how to use body language in English lessons and its value, as well as the secrets of nonverbal communication and useful special strategies that will help you gain confidence and power in any face-to-face interaction. You should also start using your experience to train others and the effect of cultural differences on body language comprehension.

Keywords: non-verbal communication, body posture, gestures, facial expressions, social rejection, crucial to success.

English language is an international language, that's why the requirements for having sufficient English language skills are improving. Communication skills are considered as the most focused skills because one must communicate fluently in order to succeed in professional interactions. All we know someone who can walk into a room full of people and within minutes give an accurate description about the relationships between those people and what they are feeling. The ability to read a person's attitudes and thoughts by their behavior was the original communication system used by humans before spoken language evolved. Our spoken language, however, recognizes how important body language is to our communication. A body language has a great role in any kind of interactions and professional interactions I chose the problem of the importance of non-verbal communication (body language) in teaching English. It has been suggested that two-thirds of our communication is nonverbal. Between head nods, smiles, frowns, closed postures, head tilts, raised hands and excited pacing, teachers, and students send hundreds of non-verbal cues to one another daily. Positive body language in a classroom setting has the ability to motivate,

inspire and engage. It can not only give you the confidence you need to teach but can also reassure your students that you actually know what you're talking about. It can even make your students feel safe and confident enough to participate in the lessons more frequently. Most leadership positions encourage body language that exudes power and confidence. Cues include standing tall, gesturing only from the waist up, keeping palms down and head straight and forward, and speaking with control. Think about a politician delivering an election speech. But when teaching, the nonverbal cues need to communicate a different type of leader. These cues convey warmth and empathy, reminding your students that you are approachable and there to help them grow.

Body language is a form of communication that doesn't involve any word, voice or writing and it consists of body posture, gestures, facial expressions, and eye movements. The process of communication which is done by body language is called Non-verbal communication in which messages can be communicated through gestures and touch, by body language or posture, by facial expression and eye contact, which are all considered types of non-verbal communication. While communicating humans send and interpret as much (even more than) non-verbal communication signals as the words we use. Non-verbal language is used throughout society by both genders, in every culture and even in professional interactions. Some non-verbal communications are subconscious and the speaker doesn't or can't control them, while other non-verbal communication signals are special techniques which are used to help an audience follow the speaker's ideas, thoughts and feelings. English teaching is a very important part of the school education, and body language plays a positive role in cultivating the students' characters in school education. Body language is a significant means through which people get to know each other and communicate with each other. To be brief, body language is a kind of language through gestures, manners and countenances, which include eye contact, facial expression, and gestures and so on. As mentioned above, our nonverbal communication occupies almost 50 percent of our daily communication while words themselves take up only 7 percent. Our bodies put forward messages so often that sometimes we communicate a lot more than we realize. The foreign language teachers are expected to perform actively in class, for example to dance joyfully, make vivid gesture as an actor. They are no longer expected to be kind

and cultivated or just stand stubbornly on the platform . In the current situation, there are three main aspects which is the need of body language in English teaching.

For a non-native learner, English learning is very boring. As the proverb goes “interest is the first teacher.” No matter in any fields, a person to be successful, first of all, he must spend a lot of time and energy. Second, he must be interested in it. The strong study interest is the prime motive power of leaning activity. It can stimulate and raise students’ study interest. Therefore, before each class, teachers should make good preparation to make sure that the students can have strong interest through a series of body language. For example, to teach: “What are you doing?” teachers can design the following body language for the context: let the students make the action of waiting, or dancing together with you. Students imitate the body language with teacher, listen and do warm up in the activities to enter the study condition, which can stimulate students’ enthusiastic of learning greatly. In the classroom, teachers’ behavior will influence students’ leaning concentration. Sometimes teachers in their teaching with the use of body language can stimulate the students’ interest. Facial expression is a “universal language” in human being’s society. Humans can show their feelings and emotions through facial expressions, such as happiness, sorrow, and fear. Therefore, teachers should know how to utilize different facial expressions to deal with different situations that appear in the classroom. If a teacher could use his facial expressions well, he would create good studying atmosphere and enhance his teaching effect. For instance, when a student gives a wrong answer, will the teacher criticize him with an angry face or just encourage him with a smile? The answer is self-evident. English studying is comparatively difficulty for most students. Thus, teachers need to keep students optimistic and perky in English learning. To keep smiling has this magical function. Some pedagogic professors proposed once, “Teachers should use smile with love to conquer a student’s mind.” A good English teacher should take the warm smile into classroom teaching.

A warm smile could give students comfy studying surroundings. How does the teacher do this? Teachers can tell students some humorous stories in English or let them give some short role-plays. Teachers and students can keep their relationships under a happy and comfy atmosphere. A philosopher once said: “Education is important but it does not mean that teachers should keep a long face in the classroom.”

When students cannot focus their attention on the text, teachers can use some grandiloquent facial expressions to draw their attentions. To sum up, if a teacher can use his facial expression diplomatically, he can receive a perfect classroom teaching result. Non-verbal language contributes very much to successful communication. Because nonverbal signals we send a lot. Non-verbal communication is a skill. In referring to communication, some people suffer from deficiencies so severe that they experience social rejection because of their poor non-verbal skills. And some demonstrate such an unusually high proficiency in nonverbal skills that they almost always excel in social interactions. Imagine that a person is being interviewed by the director of a company that he has applied for a job. First impression that the director will get from him is the appearance of his, from his style of dressing to the way he shake his hand will give a great impact on next things that he will say during conversation. Next, while he is conversing with him, he will be judged according to how he behave his voice, posture and gestures. His eye contact will show his attitude to his speech and also it helps to keep the listener's attention. While over 90% of all human communication is non-verbal, some research suggests that at least 75% of all classroom communication is non-verbal. It makes sense therefore for teachers to use non-verbal communication to their advantage in the classroom. Body language is very important in teaching English as a foreign language. Unfortunately, non-verbal communication skills aren't taught in any educational institutions, but are crucial to success in professional and social settings. In academic lyceums and high educational institutions students are mainly taught the language itself, regardless the fact that culture is the key in learning any foreign language. Every student will need to be proficient in their body language in order to succeed in their future professional life. As we learn a foreign language with the aim of being able to interact with people from foreign countries, it is essential to learn the nations' cultural peculiarities, traditions, customs and also body language etiquette. Some non-verbal language elements may be general in every culture with the same meaning and some may differ from culture to culture. These differences in those non-verbal signals and being unaware of the dissimilar meaning of same non-verbal signals may lead to misunderstandings between people.

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